

THE INFLUENCE OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON THE PERFORMANCE OF ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGE MANUFACTURING SECTOR IN TANZANIA: A CASE OF TANZANIA BREWERIES LIMITED

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6463397

Published Date: 01-April-2022

Abstract: The objective of the study on the influence of project management practices on performance of alcoholic beverage manufacturing industry in Tanzania. The study was conducted in Tanzania Breweries Limited (TBL). It was performed based on three hypotheses which are project planning, project execution and project monitoring and evaluation which were tested on organization performance. The study was performed using explanatory design through causality testing practices with the data being collected in the case study from 100 respondents. The facts were obtained using questionnaires which were structured. The collected results were computed in SPSS data sheet for generating significant statistics in filling the gap. Frequency tables and percentages as descriptive statistics were generated first and described the profile of the respondents. In addition to that, correlation and multiple regression were described to show the relationship between study variables. Findings stated that all three independent variables such as project planning, project execution and project monitoring and evaluation have positive effect and significant statistically on organization performance. This implies that organization performance in project management practices is determined by project planning, project execution and project monitoring and evaluation. The study further recommended that it is important for the organization to have adequate project management practices to assure performance in the task undertaking for the organization.

Keywords: Alcoholic beverage manufacturing, Tanzania, Project management practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Dynamic is the term that can be used to describe the current business situation (Daga, 2014). Company success is widely defined as winning in the marketplace, and firms tend to measure this with financial and economic indicators including return measures, market share measures, and stock value measures (Jugdev & Muller, 2005). The difficult economic times in today's world have made organizations to constantly change due to high level competition and environmental change caused by a lot of changes in terms of regulations and organizational restructuring (PWC, 2012). In order for organization to stay competitive under this environment, and as part of their strategy, have started moving from operations and business as usual to project management.

In the process of managing a project, the main five stages of a project life cycle which are initiation, planning, execution, monitoring and controlling and closure are forming the main part in ensuring a project is successful. All this implies the application of skills, tools, knowledge and techniques to a project in order to meet its requirements (PMBOK, 2004). When these phases are put together, they address the project path from its beginning to the end. In business, the same stages form a cyclic pattern of event which occurs in the course of developing company deliverables (Method, 2010). The phases of project management can be linked with the operation of business in such a way that; Initiation stage is that time when the organization identifies an area which needs change or improvement.

The planning stage involves envisioning the objectives, purpose, vision and mission of the change or improvement you want to achieve. It involved determining the availability of resources, budget and time (Daga, 2014). It lays down tasks of different activities by developing a workable scheme for achievement of goals. The execution/ implementation stage comes after the planning and designing of that activity to bring the intended change is done. This is stage where the actual work now is being done by transforming resources and other required materials per the work schedule to reach the project goals (Drob, 2019). The last stage is called closure or termination stage, which is the stage where the project is being disbanded after being completed. Remaining resource are being accounted for and final report is prepared.

Project management matters; leading organizations, in the world today from all sectors and geographic borders, have been steadily adopting project management as a way to monitor and control spending and improve projects results (PMI, 2010). By implementing a project management, organizations are becoming able to a strategic value chain which comes to give companies an edge above their competitors and especially in the high risk sectors and markets (PMI, 2010). Project management is key in helping an organization align well its strategies, in bringing leadership and direction to projects, in giving clear focus and objectives while executing strategic goals, in controlling quality and ensuring whatever is produced hits its mark, risk management and lastly the project management ensures project progress is being tracked and reportedly continuous to make sure it stays on track (Aston, 2017).

The history of projects is said to start since 2,500 BC, on the projects which involved the construction of the impressive Egyptian pyramids. The projects that have implemented specific aspects of project management were conducted, much later in the twentieth century, in the United States, along with the revolution of management theories (Drob, 2019). The author also mentions, Frank W. Taylor, Frank and Lillian Gilbreth, Henri Fayol and Henry Gantt as the main promoters to the appearance and development of scientific management theory. US Navy, were involved with the implementation of project management practices in the control of Polaris missile project contracts.

In the evolution of project management Sandro Azzopardi provides four periods in the development of modern project management. Prior to 1958 which is termed as Craft system to human relations? During this time Henry Gantt invented the Gantt chart and widely the Work breakdown structure (WBS) started to be widely used. In the period between 1958-1979 is application of management science (Aston, 2017). During this time there was a rapid development on computer technology seeing progression from mainframe computers to mini-computers in the 1970s where we also see Bill Gates and Paul Allen founding Microsoft in 1975. Between 1980 and 1994, the author terms this as the Production Centre Human Resources. During this time the Personal Computers (PC) were introduced with the associated communications networking facilities and made project management techniques more easily accessible. From 1995 to present the author terms this period as the creation of a new environment (Daga, 2014). This is the period where we see the development of internet which dramatically came to change the business . One of the major projects which took place during this period is the year 2000 (Y2K) project.

The ideas of organizational performance remain to take a central position in the process of managing a private or public organization. Efficiency, productivity, excellence, and total quality have become the major concerns in the western organization in the last decades (Lewis & Minton, 1986). Similarly, Richard *et al.* (2009) have documented indicators of organization performance by looking at financial performance, product market performance and shareholder return. Thus, in the modern and competitive age, project management practices becomes very important in achieving organization's objectives. This is due to the fact that it plays significant role in fostering sufficient planning process and practice, execution process, as well as effective monitoring and evaluation (Drob, 2019). However, most companies struggle in the achievement because they do business as usual and old practiseses. Therefore, the study seeks to assess the influence of project management practiseses on the performance of an organizational performance

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Several studies increasingly indicates that project management has played a main role on the success of organizations in driving change and achieving the business objectives. This is evident with Serra and Kunc (2014) that in construction projects undertaken in United Kingdom (UK) have been performing well due to effective and efficient project management practices since has been keen in ensuring effective planning, execution and assessment of the projects in a manner that guarantees effectiveness and efficiency. In addition to that, Serra and Kunc (2014) also suggest that project management practices is the key remedy towards success in any project undertaking regardless of the size, scope and the beneficiaries' types.

The ability of an organization to implement projects is what leads to the attainment of intended benefits and the achievement business goals, (PWC, 2012). Project management aims at achieving quality outcomes under the major constraints of time, scope and budget. Business as usual operation in an organization is nowhere to be tracked and measured and therefore its measurement in terms of accomplishment as planned is hard to be recognized. This is different from projects, in which its functions and activities are always initiated, planned and designed well, implemented and monitored well to the end and this makes them accomplishable within budget, time and scope.

However, due to lack of knowledge of project management, many organizations to date are still operating on business as usual (PWC, 2012). Under business as usual (BAU) operation, tasks are completed without considering much of time, budget and scope, (Harrin, 2017). They are not taken into consideration of activity planning, implementation and monitoring and evaluation. Consequently, all this tends to put the accomplishment of the organization's activities at stake of achievement and so they found themselves struggling in the competitive environment. In response to the weakness by business as usual operation, the study intends to investigate the influence that project management practices on the performance of the organization.

This prompt the need to undertake the study in Tanzanian context since several studies have been conducted on project undertaking such that Massawe (2018) assessed the effect of pre project planning on performance of construction projects in Tanzania. Also, Kalushekya (2017) assessed the effect of project value for money on the performance of construction projects in Tanzania. Since that is the case, it is vivid that little has been done on project management practices on organization performance which is the gap to be filled. Therefore, the study seeks to assess the influence of project management practices on performance of alcoholic beverage manufacturing sector in Tanzania.

1.3 Research Objectives

1.3.1 General objective

The general objective of the study was to assess the influence of project management practices on the performance of alcoholic beverage manufacturing sector in Tanzania.

1.3.2 Specific objectives

- i. To assess the influence project planning on the performance of alcoholic beverage manufacturing sector in Tanzania.
- ii. To ascertain the influence of project execution on the performance of alcoholic beverage manufacturing sector in Tanzania.
- iii. To explore the influence of project monitoring and evaluation on the performance of alcoholic beverage manufacturing sector in Tanzania.

1.4 Study Hypotheses

H1: Project planning positively influence performance of alcoholic beverage manufacturing sector in Tanzania.

H2 Project execution positively influences performance of alcoholic beverage manufacturing sector in Tanzania.

H3 Project monitoring and evaluation positively influence performance of alcoholic beverage manufacturing sector in Tanzania.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The study may serve useful to the organizations both public and private since the findings may be sufficient inputs towards improving the and conduct impacting performance. The findings of the study may be useful in fostering policy formulation on the organization to conform to the project management practices towards ensuring performance of the entities. The study may be useful in generating several others gaps for the undertaking of other studies in the future. The study may also enable the researcher to accomplish the program since it is the requirement which must be fulfilled.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study is conducted within the context of project management and evaluation in alcoholic beverage manufacturing and production sector in Tanzania. In that case, the study fits the manufacturing sector in line with project management for that matter

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.1 Theory of Constraints

Simit *et al* (2014), in their literature notes that, the Theory of constraints, can be applied in production, logistics, supply chain, distribution, project management, accounting, research and development, sales, marketing and so on. This theory was put forward in 1984 by Dr. Eliyahu M. Goldratt in his book titled 'The Goal', which focuses on helping organizations in continually achieving their goals. He adapted the concept to project management with his book critical chain which was published on 1997. The theory of constraints (TOC) is being considered as a management practices which contemplates that at any given time, an organization can be limited from achieving its highest goal by a single constraint.

This theory then provides tools which helps in identifying that constraint and breaking through it. Through this theory the managers can be assisted deciding what to change, what to change it to and how to cause the change. It gives practical and effective solutions to business problems. Murder (2011) in his article explains that, the TOC which is also known as the thinking process focuses on how quickly results can be achieved. The result on this process is known as throughput and on the other hand we say the TOC centres its attention on factors that obstruct the speed of this throughput.

Carrin and Chris (2005) explain the underlying assumption of the theory of constraints where they say organizations can be measured and controlled by variations on three measures which are throughput, operational expense and inventory. Kerzner (2000) stipulates the impossible in a real-life system by arguing the theory that, in the absence of anything to prevent a system from achieving higher throughput, its throughput would be infinite. Goldratt and Cox (1992) initiated a method called five focusing steps for addressing system problems on an ongoing basis. The steps involved are; identifying the constraint, exploiting the constraint, subordinating other activities to the constraint, elevating the constraint and lastly if anything has been broken one has to go to step one. The figure below summarizes the five focusing steps in the process of ongoing improvement.

2.1.2 Organization Theory

Organization theory tells us why organizations do take on the structures and characteristics the way they do and it also helps organizations in having certain similar characteristics (Morris, 1979). It can be defined as the study of how organizations function and their relationship with their environment. It is said to involve elements of design, culture and culture. Organizations cannot be seen. According to Daft *et al.* (2010), Organizations are social entities that, are goal-directed, are designed as deliberately structured and coordinated activity systems, and are linked to external environment. They also say that, organizations are made up of people and their relationships with one another and that managers deliberately structure and coordinate organizational resources to achieve the organization purpose.

The theory of organization helps us to have a clear understanding of an organization. As the study is going to look on organizational performance, deep understanding about an organization at this stage is very critical. According to Mintzberg (1979), an organization is made up of five components, which are; Strategic apex, middle line, techno structure, supportive staff and operating core. In explaining them all, Strategic apex is the top level of an organization comprising of CEO, CFO who are reporting to board of directors, responsible to government and its agencies and they

work to ensure the organization follows their vision, mission and manages its relationship with its environment to achieve the organizations goals.

2.2 Empirical Review

This section explores literature applicable to the variables of the study. It provides empirical evidence on the knowledge that is available from different scholars in regards to the variables of our study which are project initiation, project planning, project execution and project monitoring and evaluation.

2.2.1 Project Planning and Organizational Performance

According to Garg *et al.* (2014) assessed the role of project planning on the performance of the project undertakings. The study was performed in Ireland through survey design. Findings revealed that planning of the project is useful in fostering performance since it facilitates monitoring and evaluation as well as implementation and execution in line with value for money as being effectiveness and efficiency. This entails the gap in to be conducted in Tanzania since similar inquiry pertaining to project management practices on organization performance is performed to fill the gap in the area as well.

According to Faniran *et al.* (2010) project planning can regarded as an iterative process used to define project scope. They continue by saying project planning is also utilized to develop and refine project objectives and set the course of actions to run a project according to specific standards of quality. Baldwin and Bordoli (2014) propounds that regardless of the definition for project planning, it has the objective of achieving a number of common factors including the production of realistic schedules and costs, the completion of project as per the defined standards of quality, criteria for designing, resources available, health and safety and also meeting project stakeholder's expectation.

By meeting this expectation it will mean that the organization has performed according to the planned goals. Baldwin and Bordoli (2014), also defines project schedule as a representation of project activities identified by the work breakdown structure (WBS). Yang (2007), adds by stating the concept of project scheduling deals with logical sequencing of activities and the addition of activity duration which includes related concepts like resource loading and tracking progress during project execution.

Hill (2018) states that project planning helps an organization chart a course for the achievement of its goals. This process is said to begin with reviewing the current operations of the organization and identifying what needs to be improved operationally in the year to come. Planning involves forecasting the results which the organization wants to achieve and determining the steps necessary to arrive the intended success. The author adds by saying project planning helps in efficient use of resources, goals establishment, team building and creating competitive advantage

Kerzner (2011) suggests that in order to succeed in planning one needs to be trained in various facets of project management such as resource planning and monitoring and evaluation in order to be able to effectively manage projects. Leading organizations across sectors and geographic borders have been steadily embracing project management as a way to control spending and make project results better, (PMI, 2010).

According to PMI (2010), more than half of the executives in the economist intelligence unit report argued following a project management practice became more important since the recession began. Compared to 2007, 40% of the respondents suggested that this is the result of investing more time in project planning and due diligence.

The importance of project planning was acknowledged in early construction studies (Laufer and Tucker, 1987) where it was argued that project planning needed to be improved by taking into account more efficient management strategies in planning. Dvir *et al.* (2003) postulate that there is a strong correlation between successful project planning and the success of a project from the perspective of project stakeholders. Together with other findings on the correlation with project implementation and execution, in later studies it was confirmed that project success can be measured in view of the quality of project planning, whereas poor planning will mean uncontrollable alterations in the planning variables of time, cost and quality (Dvir and Lechler, 2004).

2.2.2 Project Execution and Organizational Performance

ITRM (2006), states project execution phase as the stage in product or project life cycle in which all tasks listed to build up deliverables are getting implemented. For this phase to come into implementation the project plan has to be approved and the resources necessary for implementation of the starting task are assembled. The project team implement the tasks

as mapped out in the project plan. This phase is said to end when a product, good, service or any activity has met the user acceptance criteria established in the performance plan and a user acceptance document has been completed.

According to SGS (2013), their service of project execution brings together a variety of skills and expertise with the objective of aiding their clients to successfully realize the transport, installation and commissioning phases of their renewable energy projects. Garner (2014), in his article Project Execution Planning: The Key to Successful Pharmaceutical Project Delivery postulates that proper planning is very critical to successful projects in the pharmaceutical industry. He continues by adding that, project execution plan (PEP) is instrumental in making sure there is team communication and interaction. The PEP communicates the documents, the map, for the execution of the entire project and providing guidance over all project's elements. The PEP is a critical tool for successful project delivery. PWC (2012), notes that improvements in any of the key issues of an organization will lead towards better implementation of an organization's practices to project management and for that matter it will improve project scope, schedule, budget, quality and business performance.

The research by PMI (2016) on Delivering value, focus on benefits during project execution confirmed the role of project manager in ensuring an organization's expected benefits are delivered when a project is completed. It notes that, the role is especially important during project execution where benefits can be derailed due to changes in business, resource challenges, or even external forces such as sudden change in customer demands which no longer align with the project's original goals.

One of the priorities to an organization is successful project execution, where by researchers have elaborated that several project success factors can impact a project all phases. Project success in the execution phase is related to the project's timely completion, on budget and within agreed level of quality (Kerzner, 2003). Shenhar and Divr (1997), propounds that the success of a project is measured in four dimensions, and project efficiency during execution and immediately after completion is one of them.

2.2.3 Project Monitoring and Evaluation and Organizational Performance

Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) are defined as integral and individually definite parts of programme preparation and implementation. They are critical tools for forward looking strategic positioning, organizational learning and for sound management, (UNICEF, 2013). A well M&E system is a very essential part of good project/programme management and accountability. Timely and reliable M&E will provide information which will help on; Supporting on project/programme implementation, contributing to organizational learning and knowledge sharing, upholding accountability and compliance, (IFRC, 2011).

Bacchus *et al.* (2010) explains the rationale of monitoring as it allows managers to track progress of projects, programmes and policies against the planned goals. When using new practices such as innovative early detection programmes, it is vital to closely monitor both intended and unintended results and also to test and revise the assumptions on which the intervention is based. The author also explains the benefits of evaluations as it involves an assessment of strength and weaknesses of projects and programmes in order to improve their effectiveness. This is a very important source of evidence of the performance of project, programme or policy.

Crawford and Bryce (2003), Kusek and Rist (2004), Joley (2003), Mohan (2001) and Marsh and David (1999), attest that M&E skills are essential requirements for organizational performance. The public service commission of South Africa (PSC, 2008), postulated the use or the purpose of monitoring and evaluation as it is used for management decision making, organizational learning and accountability. Also M&E findings can be used for soliciting support for programmes, supporting advocacy and promoting transparency.

According to (Waren, 2016), The process of planning, monitoring and evaluation make up the Result-Based Management (RBM) practices, which is intended to assist in decision making towards explicit goals. Hancock (2009) propounds that, evaluation is a very important determinant of effectiveness through an evaluation plan, the firm can clarify what direction the evaluation has to take basing on priorities, resources, time, and skills needed to accomplish the evaluation. He postulates that, in order to enhance effectiveness and transparency the management team is supposed to be actively involved in the process of monitoring and evaluation of budgetary control processes and procedures.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Paradigm

Research paradigm refers to the philosophical views on the undertaking of the scientific studies (Goodwin, 2005). The study therefore used positivism practices since the knowledge was obtained using structured instrument as the questionnaire.

3.2 Area of study

The selected area for the study was Tanzania Breweries Limited (TBL) since it has several activities as among successful manufacturing entities in the country which are conducted on daily basis instead of being performed in form of projects. Therefore, the area serves as sufficient section for the inquiry to be undertaken.

3.3 Research Design

Research design refers to the practice may be adopted to assure the generation of new knowledge in filling the study gap (Creswell, 2012). The study adopted explanatory study design because knowledge gap will be filled using causal relationship practices in assuring information gathering process.

3.4 Target Population

The population of the study consisted of participants as employees in the respective organization selected and picked as the case study for that matter. The respondents as the sample size were picked and selected from the members within the study population. In that case, the area consist of 563 employees countrywide in all its offices in the country.

3.5 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The study include employees of the organization as the sample size for the study because they are the actual members and subjects relevant for the generation of sufficient primary data to fill the study gap. They comprised of 100 respondents from different sections and departments to assure knowledge generation process for that matter. The selection of the

sample size is derived from Webb (1991) suggesting that with the population of the area comprising of 100-1000 members; 10% of the population may be used as the sample size.

Besides that, with the population of the area being between 1000-2000, 5% is allowed to be used as the sample size. In addition to that, with the population of the area being greater than 2000, 1% is required to be used as the sample size. Since that is the case, Tanzania Breweries Limited (TBL) at the moment is composed of the population between 100-1000 after retrenchment whereas 10% is the requirement of the sample size. Therefore, the sample size generated is accurate and discreet. In that note, the sample size is described using table 3.1

Table 3.1: Sample Size

S/N	Department	Number of Participants
1.	Accounts	5
2.	Finance	6
3.	Procurement	4
4.	Operations	8
5.	Logistics	29
6.	Marketing	17
7.	Sales	31
	Total	100

Source: Researcher (2019)

3.6 Data Collection Methods

The study used primary data in assuring knowledge generation process and pattern for the study because the information which were used may be the ones derived from the field. Secondary information were collected from the secondary sources in line with the study hypotheses to support the primary data in the discussion of the study results.

3.7 Pilot Study

3.7.1 Validity and Reliability

Validity and reliability are measurements for assuring data quality on study variables through accuracy determination and consistence of the study variables. Validity was first tested to assure accuracy on the study variables through validation of the questionnaire using pilot testing practices. Despite that, reliability test follows after validity to measure consistence of the study variables through Cronbach Alpha test. Therefore, the test is described using table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Cronbach Alpha Test

Study Variables	Cronbach Alpha Values
Project Planning	0.807
Project Execution	0.824
Project Monitoring and Evaluation	0.759
Organization Performance	0.743

Source: Field Data

The results in table 3.2 shows the data reliability results on study variables which is asserts that they are all reliable and consistent for that matter. This is further evident with Ritter (2010) suggesting that reliability test on study variables using Cronbach Alpha test is determined by the values of the Cronbach being 0.7 and above. Since that is the case, it is certain that the variables of the study are reliable and consistent because they are all above 0.7.

3.8 Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics specifically frequencies, percentages and mean were to show the profile of the respondents. Despite that, correlation and multiple regression analysis was performed to show the relationship between independent variables on the dependent variable. The study is basically quantitative.

4. STUDY RESULTS, DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Respondents Profile

This provides the overview of the employees in Tanzania Breweries Limited (TBL) in Dar es Salaam Office as respondents whereas the study used specifically three variables of age, gender the education level in describing the profile for that matter. In that case, the profile is describes in the manner which is as follows.

4.1.1 Age

The study expected to generate results on age of the respondents whereas the facts are described in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
21-35	40	40.0
36-50	58	58.0
50+	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Field Data

The study results in table 4.1 describes the facts on age which provides that 40 respondents (40%) were aged between 21-35 years; while 58 respondents (58%) were aged between 36-50 years; and 2 respondents (2%) were above 50 years of age. This implies that most employees in Tanzania Breweries Limited (TBL) constitutes of individuals residing in the productive and active age groups in most cases than the aged ones.

The statement is acknowledged by TBL (2018) stating that the entity is business oriented, factory and consist most of sales and operations activities whereas in most cases it required individuals who are strong and active in fostering the realization of goals and objectives. In that regard, most employees in the organization usually range within active age than the aged ones.

4.1.2 Gender

To avoid biasness the Researcher found it necessary to involve both males and females. The respondents were requested to state the information which is well illustrated using table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	74	74.0
Female	26	26.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Field Data

Study results in table 4.2 indicated information on gender of the respondents whereas male as respondents were 74 (74%); while female as respondents were 26 (26%). This implies that Tanzania Breweries Limited (TBL) despite the fact that it is a factory and or manufacturing entity it is open to all people as being both men and women to join the entity as employees. This is certain since the policy is that way provided that the distinction is based on the demonstration of the ability to deliver and work to be recruited and be part of the team

This is evident with Mutegi (2015) providing that Tanzania Breweries Limited (TBL) as the organization policy wise is not bound to gender related issues since it is an entity free to all people regardless of the their gender to become part of the team as employee(s). Though, the concern is that merit is the only determinant for anyone to be part of the team because it is a business entity whereas it has to make sure that anyone employed fits well to the hired position to ensure that the company performs well in the business.

4.1.3 The Level of Education

The study further collected information on level of education of the respondents whereas table 4.3 illustrates the results.

Table 4.3: Education

Level of Education	Frequency	Percent
Certificate	3	3.0
Diploma	7	7.0
First Degree	51	51.0
Masters	39	39.0
Total	100	100.0

Source: Field Data

Study results in table 4.3 shows facts on the level of education on the respondents that 3 respondents (3%) were certificate holders; while 7 respondents (7%) were diploma holders; 51 respondents (51%) were first degree holders; and 39 respondents (39%) were master's degree holders. The implication of the study results is that procurement activities in Tanzania Breweries Limited (TBL) and other activities in the organization are handled by highly skilled and qualified individuals as employees. Though, the organization also provides placements for young people willing to volunteer and practice in working in the company in the process of undertaking their college and university education.

This is supported by Mugabe (2012) stating that Tanzania Breweries Limited (TBL) is keen in all its operations, units, sections and departments such that practitioners hired as employees are usually skilled and highly competent to make sure that the company excels higher in business through profitability generation for that matter. This has been the remedy in ensuring high performance in Tanzanian market pertaining to the business.

4.2 Findings, Analysis and Discussion of the Study Hypotheses

The presentation of findings and analysis of the study hypotheses is illustrated through measures of central tendency being mean and standard deviation; and also by means of inferential analysis. Therefore, the description of the findings is as follows.

4.2.1 Mean and Standard Deviation

The analysis is performed to reveal the variable among the independent ones with larger influence than others in the set of data which is illustrated in table 4.

Table 4.4: Mean and Standard Deviation

Study Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	N
Organization Performance	3.182	.1025	100
Project Planning	3.484	.1352	100
Project Execution	3.528	.1447	100
Project Monitoring and Evaluation	3.657	.1592	100

Source: Field Data

The findings on mean and standard deviation provide that practices to project monitoring and evaluation consist of larger influence as the independent variable than other variables in the category on organization performance which is the dependent variable. This is certain because the variable has larger mean value than others (3.657). The implication is that organization performance through project management practices is largely influenced by project monitoring and evaluation. Regardless of that, standard deviation provides that the variance on the study variables in their value is less than 3 and is not high. This implies that respondents' opinion did not differ much.

4.2.2 Inferential Analysis

The analysis is performed to point out the relationship between study variables through correlation and multiple regression. However, the overall influence of the study independent variables is performed on organization performance as the dependent variable first which is described through model summary test in table 4.5 below.

Table 4.5: Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of Estimate	Change Statistics			Durbin- Watson
1	.643	.595	.590	49.921	.503	45.105	.000	1.583

Source: Field Data

The study findings in the overall testing of the study variables which is provided by the value of R^2 that organization performance in project management practices is fostered by project planning, project execution and project monitoring and evaluation by 59.5%. This implies that the assumptions of the study in their totality on organization performance as the dependent variable have positively being attained.

4.2.2.1 Multiple Regression Analysis

This is performed to show the influence of all independent variables distinctly on project performance as the dependent variable. Also, the analysis is intended to correct the multicollinearity error through the value of VIF with the results shown in table 4.6.

Table 4.6: Multiple Regression

Model	Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	VIF
	B	Std. error	Beta			
(constant)	-10.036	3.263		-1.089	.123	
Project Planning	1.930	.283	.503	12.184	.000	3.007
Project Execution	2.103	.307	.518	12.336	.000	2.825
Project Monitoring and Evaluation	2.404	.341	.543	12.503	.000	2.628

Source: Field Data

The findings of the study provide that all three independent variables such as project planning, project execution and project monitoring and evaluation are positive with statistical significant effect on organization performance with $p < 0.05$. This implies that organization performance through project management practices is facilitated by project planning, project execution and project monitoring and evaluation.

4.3 Discussion of the Findings**4.3.1 Project Planning and Organization Performance**

The findings revealed that project planning has positive effect and significant statistically on organization performance ($p < 0.05$). This implies that organization performance through project management practices is influenced by project planning. This is complemented by Hemmati (2002) stating that project management practices is essential in fostering organization performance through planning because the stage is essential in facilitating the adequate identification of the stakeholders to facilitate the conduct of the project.

Kerzner (2003) also provide that project management practices is very important to be included to ensure its performance outcomes because in planning stakeholders are among the key actors to be well identified and assessed on their involvement in ensuring positive outcomes on the project undertaking. This is necessary because it enables the clear identification of relevant stakeholders as actors for the performance of the projects and the organization at large.

4.3.2 Project Execution and Organization Performance

The findings indicates that project execution has positive effect on the organization performance of the as the dependent variable whereas $p < 0.05$. This implies that organization performance through project management practices is facilitated by project execution whereas Carr (2009) provides that in project undertakings there can be shortcomings and challenges in their executions which are necessary to be predicted and assessed before the planning of the project starts for ensuring positive outcomes.

In that case, project management practices is useful in this since it facilitates the selection and consideration of several alternatives in case of tragedies and shortcomings for that matter. In addition to that, Filicetti (2009) on the other hand suggest that any project undertaking there must be alternatives as response to the predicted scenarios that may be a barrier to the project undertaking for that matter for performance specifically in their executions.

4.3.3 Project Monitoring and Evaluations and Organization Performance

The study indicate that project monitoring and evaluations as the independent variable has a positive significant effect on organization performance with $p < 0.05$. This implies that organization performance through project management practices is influenced by project monitoring and evaluation. This is supported by Banks (2017) stating that project management is an essential component in execution and preparation of the project because it ensures the inclusion of the right practices to project design to assure adequate monitoring and evaluation. This is an important and necessary component since it assures the assessment of the project prior to the outcomes through value for money and several other components useful for performance outcomes.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the Study

This is the description of the study on the influence of project management practices on performance of alcoholic beverage manufacturing industry in Tanzania. The study was conducted in Tanzania Breweries Limited (TBL). It was performed based on three hypotheses which are project planning, project execution and project monitoring and evaluation which were tested on organization performance. The study was performed using explanatory design through causality testing practices with the data being collected in the case study from 100 respondents. The facts were obtained using questionnaires which were structured.

The collected results were computed in SPSS data sheet for generating significant statistics in filling the gap. Frequency tables and percentages as descriptive statistics were generated first and described the profile of the respondents. In addition to that, correlation and multiple regressions were described to show the relationship between study variables. Findings stated that all three independent variables such as project planning, project execution and project monitoring and evaluation have positive effect and significant statistically on organization performance. This implies that organization performance in project management practices is determined by project planning, project execution and project monitoring and evaluation.

5.2 Conclusion of the Study

It is certain and vivid that project management practices positively influences organization performance in alcoholic beverage industry. This is evident with the fact that all three aspects which were tested on organization performance through project management practices such as project planning, project execution and project monitoring and evaluation have been generated as positive and significant statistically on organization performance. Since that is the case, it is perceived that project management practices must be highly ensured and adhered in the project undertaking for the purpose of making sure that all projects gets to achieve a great deal of performance in organizations.

5.3 Recommendations of the Study

Since project management practices is essential on organization performance, the study recommends that the component should be included on mandatory basis as the requirement to be fulfilled for the purpose of being certain an assured of the outcomes. This is important because most manufacturing industry projects have been faced with massive cost overrun, and various forms of underperformance such as delays, underperformance and poor standards as far as outcomes is concerned. This may be severely eradicated once the assessment is embedded from the project management practices stages and followed by the actual realities in commencing projects.

5.4 Areas for Further Studies

The study has been conducted through explanatory design which is basically quantitative practices whereas the other study may be undertaken using exploratory design through qualitative practices in ensuring knowledge gap filling. Despite that, the study also has focused on project management practices effect on the performance of the organization based on manufacturing industry. However, another study may be performed in the same direction in another industry such as construction, education, health and others.

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